

Massive galaxy formation along the cosmic web filaments at $z=3$

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0. Introduction:

Cosmic web and the SSA22 proto-cluster

1. The cosmic web filaments in ADF22

2. ALMA views of a giant LAB, SSA22-LAB1

3. QGs within the cosmic web filaments

0. Introduction

Introduction: galaxy growth within the cosmic web

*Ly α surface brightness map in a proto-cluster
by the FOREVER22 simulation
Yajima, Umehata et al. MNRAS, 2022*

*Cold gas map around a $z=3.6$ galaxy
Cadiou et al. MNRAS, 2022, 514, 5429*

- ❖ Large-scale filamentary structure is a fundamental prediction.
- ❖ Interrelation between galaxies and the cosmic web is of critical importance.

A remarkable proto-cluster in SSA22

Yamada et al, 2012, AJ, 143, 79

cf: Scott Chapman's talk

- ❖ The SSA22 proto-cluster has a 3D structure traced by LAEs at $z=3.1$.
- ❖ One of the most significant overdensity at $z>2$.
=> A unique laboratory to investigate 'environmental effect'.

ALMA Deep Field in SSA22 (ADF22)

Umehata et al. 2015, ApJ, 815, L8

❖ A remarkable ($\sim 1000x$ of the average) dust-obscured star-formation and accretion activity.

=> First ALMA identification of SMG overdensity in a proto-cluster at high-z.

1. The Cosmic Web Filaments

Cosmic Web: CO Tomography

ALMA 1.1mm Map

'3D' map of DSFGs at z=3.09

Cosmic Web: MUSE results

SCAM

MUSE

Star: Dusty star-forming galaxies
and/or X-ray AGNs

Cosmic Web: The image of the cosmic web

ALMA+MUSE

MUSE 3D View

Umehata et al. 2019, Science, 366, 97

Nature of the cosmic web: 3D distribution

Umehata et al. 2019, Science, 366, 97

- ❖ Ly α emission is widely distributed into the intergalactic space.
- ❖ Ly α emission and galaxies are also correlated in 3D.
- ❖ Fainter filaments are kinematically cooler.

Nature of the cosmic web: Power source

- ❖ Based on a simple Cloudy modeling, we suggest that the Ly α emission can be explained by fluorescence if the radiation field is boosted ($x > 12$).
- ❖ Since there are 16 SMGs and 8 X-ray AGNs, they can provide sufficient amounts of ionizing photons.

Caveats:

- escape fraction of ionizing photons is unclear.
- other power sources are not excluded.

Mpc-scale gas filaments in the proto-cluster

- ❖ Ly α gas filaments are found on Mpc-scales taken with VLT/MUSE and Subaru/Suprime-Cam. It is now possible for us to catch such “filaments of the cosmic web” directly in emission.
- ❖ A variety of galaxies are indeed physically associated with the filaments, which suggest fueling from the cosmic web play a key role in shaping galaxy evolution.
- ❖ The plentiful amount of possible ionizing photon sources (e.g., DSFGs and AGNs) suggests that fluorescence scenario can account for the observed levels of Ly α emission.

2. Giant Ly α Blobs

LAB1: A giant LABs in the proto-cluster

Steidel et al. 2000, ApJ, 532, 170; Matsuda et al. 2004, AJ, 128, 569; Chapman et al. 2004, ApJ, 606, 85; Hayes et al. 2011, Nature, 476, 304; Geach et al. 2016, ApJ, 832, 37; Kubo et al. 2016, MNRAS, 455, 3333; Umehata et al. 2021, ApJ, 918, 69, and more.

- ❖ Brightest extended Ly α nebulae, LAB1 and LAB2, have some offset from the Ly α filaments in ADF22.
 - ❖ The Ly α surface brightness is much brighter than the filaments (~ 1 dex or more).
 - ❖ DSFGs are associated, but much fainter than the filaments (mostly sub-mJy.)
- => what are we seeing in LAB1?

[CII] views of LAB1

Umehata et al. 2021, ApJ, 918, 69

- ❖ ALMA Band8 observations uncovers [CII] complex across the central 100 kpc area.
 - Multiple-merging would be ongoing in LAB1.
 - [CII] emission is widely distributed than stellar emissions, which can account for tidal tails and/or recycled gas.

LAB1: Site of hierarchical galaxy assembly

Umehata et al. 2021, ApJ, 918, 69

- ❖ While M^*-M_{halo} relation suggests $M_{\text{halo}} > 10^{13} M_{\text{sun}}$, the velocity separation is narrower than the corresponding M_{halo} .
- ❖ The galaxy group in LAB1 would be in a merging phase during hierarchical galaxy assembly in the node of the cosmic web (as expected for progenitors of BCGs).
(Caveat: line of sight effect.)

LAB1: the origin of Ly α emission

❖ Our ALMA results support the “central heating source” scenario (e.g., Hayes et al. 2011, Geach et al. 2016).

I. Spectroscopically confirmed dusty star-forming galaxies as a LAB1 member.

II. The total SFR (UV+IR, 300 M_{\odot} /yr) may account for the observed Ly α luminosity.

$$L_{\text{Ly}\alpha} [\text{erg s}^{-1}] = f_{\text{esc, Ly}\alpha} \times 1.89 \times 10^{42} \times \text{SFR} [M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}]$$

III. The Ly α profile shows a dominant red peak and a blue bump. This can be interpreted as an outflow (and extinction at the systemic redshift).

LAB1: the origin of Ly α emission

❖ ...But there are also caveat.

I. fesc, Ly α 20% may be difficult, considering the dusty nature.

II. More bright SMGs in ADF22 (with SFR up to 2000 Msun/yr) are generally associated with fainter Ly α emission.

❖ We suggest cooling radiation induced by gravitational interactions an additional power source as suggested by a simulation.

A giant LAB in the proto-cluster

- ❖ A brightest LAB in the proto-cluster, LAB1, is much brighter in Ly α than the filament in ADF22. Meanwhile it is not so bright in IR.
- ❖ Recent ALMA surveys uncovers widely distributed cool ISMs in dust continuum and [CII], showing the regime is quite dynamic. LAB1 would be a node of the cosmic web where multiple-merging events are ongoing.
- ❖ A plausible scenario of Ly α power source for such a bright part is central heating and scattering. However, there must be additional factor make LAB1 spectacular. Cooling radiation associated with mergers is a candidate.

3. QGs in the proto-cluster

QGs in the proto-cluster

Sky distributions of QG candidates in the SSA22 proto-cluster

Kubo et al. ApJ, 2013, 778, 170

“AzTEC14 Group”

ALMA 1mm + MUSE Ly α map
Umehata et al. Science, 2019, 366, 97

QGs in the proto-cluster

The (rest-) UVJ diagram for QG1, QG2
 Kubo, Umehata et al. *ApJ*, 2022, 935, 89

Finding Chart of the AzTEC14 Group
 Kubo, Umehata et al. *MNRAS*, 2017, 469, 2235

The case of QG1

MOSFIRE H-/K- band spectra of QG1
Kubo, Umehata et al. ApJ, 2021, 919, 6

- ❖ Discovered spectral features of QG1 include the followings:
 - $z=3.0922$, which unambiguously places QG1 in the protocluster (and associated with the Ly α filaments).
 - While the 4000 \AA break is strong, Balmer absorption features are significant.

The case of QG1

Kubo, Umehata et al. *ApJ*, 2021, 919, 6

- ❖ Its quiescent nature is also confirmed by the non-detection by ALMA at 1.1mm.
- ❖ Models suggest a sudden quenching of the star-formation at ~ 0.6 Gyrs ago.

The case of QG1

Kubo, Umehata et al. MNRAS, 2017, 469, 2235
Kubo et al. 2018, ApJ, 867, 1

MOIRCS Ks (w/o AO)

IRCS K' (w/ AO)

❖ The rest-frame size is $re=1.37 \pm 0.75$ kpc, which is more compact than other QGs at lower redshift.

❖ Strong size evolution is required to have a larger size at $z \sim 0$.

The case of QG2

- ❖ A spectacular ionized outflow is detected in [OIII], which is broad ($W_{80} > 1000$ km/s), bright ($\text{Log} L_{[OIII]} / \text{erg/s} = 43.4$), and extended (15 pkpc).
- ❖ A QSO is powered after the shutdown of the star-formation and help complete the quenching of massive QGs at high- z .

QGs in the proto-cluster

- ❖ QGs are confirmed to coexist within the gas filaments and also within the dense galaxy group. How to maintain the quiescence under the gas-rich environment is still unclear.
- ❖ QGs are suggested to experience a sudden quenching. A plausible mechanism is negative AGN feedback, which is also in line with recent JWST results.
- ❖ The QGs seems to be on the track of the size evolution. They would experience significant size growth via minor/major merging events.

Summary

Introduction

- Direct imaging of the cosmic web is a key.
- SSA22 proto-cluster offers an invaluable target.

Ly α filaments

- HI filaments connecting a number of growing galaxies/AGNs are found.
- Fueling from the filaments can grow galaxies, and ionizing photons generated by the galaxies and illuminate the filaments.

A giant LAB

- Recent ALMA surveys confirmed that LAB1 is not so bright in FIR, in spite of the tremendous Ly α surface brightness.
- ALMA also uncovers extended and complicated nature of ISMs. LAB1 can be a site of hierarchical galaxy assembly in a massive halo.

QGs

- Two QGs have been spectroscopically confirmed in the vicinity of the filaments.
- A sudden quenching is required in such a gas-rich environment. AGN can be a key.